

From Black Box to Toolbox: Human-Centered Explainability in Developer-Authored Agent Rules

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As AI agents permeate software development, developers are embracing markdown-based rule files (e.g., *AGENTS.md*) to provide the organizational context that general-purpose models often lack. This emerging practice, nonetheless, is undermined by a critical explainability challenge. Through a qualitative study of 12 professional software developers who author agent rules for their respective projects, we found that developers lack a reliable way to verify whether an agent consistently follows specific rules. Furthermore, they struggle to attribute observable agent behaviors to individual instructions in agent rule files. Instead, they often rely on subjective "vibe checks" to test these rules. Our findings also highlight a lack of centralized governance of agent rules for common libraries, leading to redundant work and the erosion of a shared understanding about agent behavior. We argue for a transition toward rigorous rule traceability and library-level governance to transform agent customization from an ad-hoc craft into an evidence-based practice within the agentic software development lifecycle (SDLC).

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Human-Centered AI; Explainable AI (XAI); Software Engineering; AI Agents

1 Introduction

Enterprise AI integration is hindered by a misalignment: LLMs possess vast general knowledge but lack proprietary organizational context, often leading to solutions that violate internal standards. Agent rules, often stored in markdown files like *AGENTS.md*, bridge this gap, serving as persistent "context macros" and a surrogate for organizational memory. These rules act as a foundational "constitution," providing a structured framework of instructions, constraints, and personas that dictate how agents perceive context and execute actions.

Within Google, agent rules are organized in a two-tier hierarchy: project-level rules establish a shared baseline for all contributors of the project and managed as part of the codebase, while user-level rules allow for convenient personalization across projects without the burden of code review. As of late 2025, Google developers had created over 11,000 project-level agent rule files, reflecting a growing need to customize AI agents' default behavior.

This paper provides qualitative insights into how developers author and verify agent rules. We investigate the tension between intent and model compliance and propose several conceptual designs to mitigate the explainability challenges identified. Using a human-centered lens, we examine the triadic relation between the developer, the agent, and team norms to surface the causal ambiguities that arise across the agentic software development lifecycle (SDLC).

2 Related Work

Recent advancements in Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI) have shifted the research focus from providing passive transparency to enabling active human control and actionability. Watkins et al. [8] propose the "Action and Control via Explanations" (ACE) paradigm, arguing that explanations should specifically guide users to modify their inputs—such as semantic frames—to align the AI's processing with human intent. In safety-critical contexts, Schneider et al.[6] emphasize that such targeted explanations are prerequisites for stakeholders to negotiate accountability and

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maintain effective control over automated systems. These perspectives highlight that for developers authoring agent rules, explainability must function as a dynamic feedback loop for engineering behavior rather than a static report of model decision-making. Furthermore, the literature reveals that users often resort to ad-hoc strategies to manage this control when standard tooling is absent, as is the case of agent rules authoring. Benk et al. [1] observed that domain experts frequently employ "creative uses" of AI, actively shaping inputs based on often flawed mental models (e.g., assuming simple keyword matching) to steer system outputs. This mirrors our finding that developers 'shout' at the AI model via capitalization to enforce constraints. To support more rigorous steering, researchers have advocated for counterfactual explanations that allow users to simulate how input changes affect outcomes [4], and data-centric approaches that expose the processing steps preceding the model [2]. While emerging work explores using LLMs to generate narrative explanations [9] or act as "devil's advocates" [7] to critique outputs, there remains a lack of specialized tooling that bridges the gap between ad-hoc input shaping and systematic rule engineering. Our work addresses this gap within the context of agentic software development by investigating the specific friction points developers face when moving from casual tinkering to rigorous customization of agent behavior.

3 Methodology

To capture the nuances of agent behavior customization and explainability, we conducted a qualitative study with 12 Google developers (P01–P12) actively practicing agent rule-authoring on behalf of their respective teams. Data collection involved in-depth, semi-structured interviews grounded in specific, recent rule changes—such as additions, deletions, or revisions. This approach allowed us to move past hypothetical preferences to observe real-world scenarios. Our cohort of "power users" spanned diverse domains (e.g., Frontend, Backend, Security) and product teams (e.g., YouTube, Android, Wearables, etc). Our participants possessed significant institutional knowledge: 70% have at least four years of tenure at Google. These participants are also sophisticated AI users with 90% utilizing AI agents daily and all had authored or edited rule files within the 90 days preceding the study, ensuring familiarity with current tooling limitations. Our inquiry focused on four areas: developer motivations, rule efficacy, rule authoring and verification practices, and friction points throughout the agent rule life cycle.

4 Findings

Our interviews reveal that developers author rules with four primary expectations: bridging the "organizational context gap," leveraging hierarchical memory to minimize repetition, prioritizing collaborative interaction over immediate coding, and serving as living documentation for onboarding. However, four critical challenges impede their ability to meet these goals:

- (1) Anticipating rule impact on agent behavior
- (2) Attributing agent behavior to specific rules
- (3) Validating agent rules systematically
- (4) Finding authoritative sources of agent rules

These challenges exacerbate the lack of explainability in agent behavior and undermine the usefulness of agent rules as an accessible mechanism for end-user customization. In the rest of this section, we elaborate on these expectations and challenges.

4.1 Developer Expectations of Agent Rules

Our study revealed four primary drivers for rule adoption and an explainability paradox.

4.1.1 Bridging the organizational context gap. A dominant reason to create agent rules, cited by 11 participants, is to impose internal constraints on technology choices. For example: "TensorFlow always means the internal google3 version; disregard external TensorFlow packages." As P07 noted, they had to instruct the agent to disambiguate to prevent it from importing from an open-source framework that had the same name as the internal one. P10 echoed this sentiment, stating that until rule files were implemented, the agent was unaware of the "legal" ways to operate within their organization's 10-plus internal variations of a given task.

4.1.2 The "DRY" Principle. Developers apply the 'Don't Repeat Yourself' (DRY) principle to their interactions with the agent: by leveraging global configurations through agent rules, they ensure that high-level instructions and parameters automatically cascade down, saving them from redundant writing. Similarly, P06 noted bundling frequent commands to avoid repetition. For example: "When I say 'run tests', execute `blaze test //my/project/...`. When I say 'build project', execute `blaze build //my/project:all`."

4.1.3 Prioritizing Collaborative Interaction Over Immediate Coding. In our study, 5 out of 12 participants explicitly rejected agents that "jump straight to coding." Instead, they want an agent that acts as a "buddy" by asking clarifying questions before writing code through rules like the following: "Act like a pair programmer: discuss the plan and ask questions to resolve ambiguities *before* implementing." Developers instruct the agent to explain its limitations, speak up if unsure, and explicitly signal why it is unsure to trigger a meaningful human-in-the-loop intervention.

4.1.4 Living Documentation and the Explainability Paradox. A majority of participants (7/12) use agent rules as a human onboarding tool, acting as a "memo" to clarify outdated team documentation. P12 noted that even when the AI fails to execute instructions, the rules remain valuable as human-readable architectural overviews. This reveals a profound contradiction: rule files are sufficiently articulated to onboard humans, yet the agent's failure to adhere to them exposes a gap between human-comprehensible intent and model compliance. This paradox is deepened by the "AI Writing AI" phenomenon, with 100% of participants using AI to author these rules. Consequently, AI is generating documentation that is legible to humans but functionally opaque to the agents themselves.

4.2 Challenges

4.2.1 Difficulty anticipating rule impact on agent behavior. A primary explainability challenge lies in "root-causing" undesirable agent behaviors—dissecting actions to hypothesize which rule modifications will trigger intended changes. To construct effective agent rules, developers require explainability regarding instructions: identifying which rules work best, determining optimal phrasing, and assessing if structural order impacts how the agent interprets multi-step plans. For example, our study reveals a notable failure: Negative Constraints (e.g., "NEVER import X") frequently fail (6/12 participants). In contrast, adjusting the agent's persona is surprisingly effective. P10's "blunt communication style" rule—instructing the agent to "remove politeness fluff"—successfully altered behavior. This suggests semantic framing is often more powerful than procedural rigidity. However, the lack of formal explainability for these interpretive nuances leaves developers without a systematic methodology for identifying or sharing best practices.

4.2.2 Difficulty Attributing agent behavior to specific rules. Another core challenge is the opacity of the agent's decision-making process. The inherent "black box" nature of LLM reasoning, where the link between an instruction and the

final output is often difficult to inspect and verify, creates an attribution problem that makes it nearly impossible for a developer to identify which directive in the agent rule file led to a particular response or triggered a tool call. Without a clear trace back to the source instruction, debugging undesirable behavior becomes a matter of guesswork rather than rigorous engineering.

4.2.3 Difficulty to validate rules systematically. The most significant pain point, shared by all 12 participants, is the inability to scientifically verify if a rule is working consistently across many session of human-AI interactions. Currently, testing agent rules is a disorganized process relying on "vibe checks"—subjective impressions developers make to determine if the agent is performing better with specific rules.

A typical 'vibe checking' process consists of modifying rule files and prompting the agent, then qualitatively assessing whether the output aligns with the underlying intent. Developers are often unable to distinguish a genuine fix from a fluke. As P02 noted, "I can't say that I actually did it the correct way... how do I validate that my agent rule is useful?" This frustration stems from the non-deterministic nature of LLMs. P05 noted that because the process is 'very unstructured,' the same task can yield different results without any rule changes, making it unclear 'what is working and what is not.'

4.2.4 Difficulty finding authoritative sources of agent rules. A lack of centralized agent rules for core libraries forces teams to independently "teach" AI agents how to use technologies that might not be common externally but part of a specific organization's core technology stack. This decentralization creates massive inefficiency, as developers across the organization redundantly rewrite basic usage rules, trapping expertise in silos. Without library-level ownership, developers face a persistent explainability gap, unable to discern if a failure stems from their own prompting, their rule file, or model hallucination.

5 Discussion and Future Work: A Rule Engineering Framework

To transition agent rule authoring from an ad-hoc craft into a rigorous discipline, we propose a Rule Engineering Framework structured around three pillars: Traceable Attribution, Empirical Validation, and Systemic Governance.

5.1 Pillar 1: Traceable Attribution

The primary bottleneck in rule authoring is the "black box" nature of agent outputs. Without a direct link between behavior and instruction, developers lack the diagnostic clarity required to iteratively refine and optimize rule logic. We propose a traceability interface where developers select a specific rule to visualize its global footprint across a file—supplemented by bidirectional links from code back to the source rule. This replaces line-by-line guesswork with a "root-cause" trail showing exactly how specific instructions trigger code fragments, thereby addressing the attribution problem. We plan to further assess the feasibility and visibility of transparent attribution by asking participants of the original study—experienced software engineers—to share their existing agent rule manifests and corresponding code outputs. We will then reverse-engineer these interactions, asking the agent to reflect on its own decision-making process to identify which specific rules triggered each line of generated code. This approach is grounded in recent research on Deliberative Alignment [3] and Critic-in-the-loop workflows [5], which demonstrates that models can be trained to provide auditable evidence for their outputs. By comparing these agent-generated "reflection logs" against the developers' actual intent, we can evaluate whether automated self-attribution is a timely and accurate substitute for manual "vibe checks."

Fig. 1. **Conceptual Evaluation Interface.** The design features a side-by-side "Diff View" for comparing agent outputs, alongside controls to toggle or edit individual rules for real-time counterfactual testing.

5.2 Pillar 2: Empirical Validation

The non-deterministic nature of LLMs makes it difficult to distinguish a genuine logic fix from a statistical fluke. The Validation Pillar addresses this uncertainty through comparative and robust testing. We propose side-by-side delta highlights (Fig. 1) to enable real-time counterfactual testing. By toggling or editing individual rules, developers can isolate specific variables, facilitating the comparison of diverse rule configurations. Furthermore, statistical batch testing replaces anecdotal "trial-and-error" with data-driven science. By automating dozens of runs using input permutations—such as swapping rule orders or using synonyms—this method generates reliable success rates (e.g., accuracy %) rather than relying on a single interaction.

5.3 Pillar 3: Systemic Governance

The current rule authoring practice is often siloed, leading to inconsistent instructions and redundant efforts. The Governance Pillar centralizes expertise and automates context discovery to solve the authoritative source problem. This begins with eliminating the friction of manual rule entry through AI-driven codebase scanning and rule recommendations. By auto-discovering context and presenting a draft for conversational refinement, this paradigm transforms the developer's role from a manual author into a high-level editor.

Furthermore, we propose a shift in library-level ownership, moving the burden of rule authoring from end-consumers to technology maintainers. Much like header files in traditional software development, maintainers should provide agent rule manifests to ensure systemic correctness and prevent the fragmentation of expertise across team silos. Finally, to maintain high standards, interactive auditing via a "presubmit review agent" should be employed. This agent flags

known anti-patterns—such as ineffective negative constraints—before rules are committed to the codebase, ensuring the integrity of the entire engineering lifecycle.

6 Conclusion

Our study reveals that bridging the 'organizational context gap' requires shifting agent rule authoring from ad-hoc experimentation to a rigorous engineering practice. We propose a three-part approach: traceable attribution, empirical validation, and systemic governance. Providing this level of explainability and rigor is critical to establishing the reliability necessary for the integration of AI agents into the professional software development lifecycle.

References

- [1] Michaela Benk, Raphael P. Weibel, and Andrea Ferrario. 2022. Creative Uses of AI Systems and their Explanations: A Case Study from Insurance. In *Proceedings of the 2022 CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI '22)*. ACM, New York, NY, USA.
- [2] Nadja Geisler and Carsten Binnig. 2025. XAI meets Data-Centric AI: The Need to Explain Data Processing. In *Proceedings of the 5th CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI '25)*. ACM, New York, NY, USA.
- [3] Maosen Guan, Mrinmaya Joglekar, Eric Wallace, Saachi Jain, Boaz Barak, Alec Helyar, Ricardo Dias, et al. 2024. Deliberative Alignment: Reasoning Enables Safer Language Models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.16339* (2024). <https://openai.com/index/deliberative-alignment/>
- [4] Orfeas Menis Mastromichalakis, Jason Liartis, and Giorgos Stamou. 2024. Beyond One-Size-Fits-All: Adapting Counterfactual Explanations to User Objectives. In *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI '24)*. ACM, New York, NY, USA.
- [5] OpenAI et al. 2024. Training LLMs for Honesty via Confessions. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.14620* (2024). <https://openai.com/index/how-confessions-can-keep-language-models-honest/>
- [6] Lena Schneider, Daniel Boos, and Gudela Grote. 2024. Establishing Control via Targeted Explanations: How XAI enables Stakeholder Negotiations about the Distribution of Accountability and Control in Safety-Critical Domains. In *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI '24)*. ACM, New York, NY, USA.
- [7] Ashley Suh, Kenneth Alperin, Harry Li, and Steven R. Gomez. 2025. Don't Just Translate, Agitate: Using Large Language Models as Devil's Advocates for AI Explanations. In *Proceedings of the 5th CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI '25)*. ACM, New York, NY, USA.
- [8] Elizabeth Anne Watkins, Emanuel Moss, Ramesh Manuvinakurike, Meng Shi, Richard Beckwith, and Giuseppe Raffa. 2024. ACE, Action and Control via Explanations: A Proposal for LLMs to Provide Human-Centered Explainability for Multimodal AI Assistants. In *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI '24)*. ACM, New York, NY, USA.
- [9] Alexandra Zyteck, Sara Pidò, and Kalyan Veeramachaneni. 2024. LLMs for XAI: Future Directions for Explaining Explanations. In *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI '24)*. ACM, New York, NY, USA.